

An Improved Method of Preparation of Substituted Amides and Hydrazides.

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Of all the methods available for the preparation of diaryl carbamides, those involving the use of urea and other derivatives of carbonic acid (*e.g.*, urethane, carbonic ester, phenylurea, phenylcarbonate, carbonyl chloride, etc.) are recommended since these can be easily procured and give satisfactory yields. (Hoffman and Steiner, *Annalen*, 1848, 70, 138; Hentzschel, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, ii, 27, 499; Claus, *Annalen*, 1875, 179, 126; Wilm and Wischin, *Annalen*, 1868, 147, 160; Bender, *Ber.*, 1880, 13, 699; Eckenroth, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 516; Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1864, 131, 252; Weith, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 821; Manuelli, Ricca-Rosellini, *Gazzetta*, 1890, 29, II, 126; Frerichs, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1899, 237, 316).

In connection with another piece of work, the preparation of *pp*-diacetaminodiphenylurea was attempted after the method of Schiff and Ostrogovitch (*Annalen*, 1896, 293, 376) which consists in heating acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine with urea, but most of the product was found to be insoluble in boiling hydrochloric acid. The substitution of phenyl carbonate or urethane (*cf.* Eckenroth; Manuelli and Ricca-Rosellini, *loc. cit.*) for urea gave no better result. The action of carbonyl chloride in toluene solution upon acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine (*cf.* Hoffman; Hentzschel, *loc. cit.*) gave a dark coloured amorphous mass. In all these cases it was found very difficult to control the reaction and so the use of a liquid reaction medium was thought of and the action of urea upon acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine was tried in boiling *isoamyl* alcohol. The beautifully crystalline product obtained in this reaction (m.p. 344°) could be completely hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid.

It was thought worth while to try the general applicability of this method in bringing about condensation between divers types of amines, diamines, hydrazines, thiosemicarbazides, etc., on the one hand and amides like urea, thiourea, oxamide, malonamide, succinamide, acetamide, benzamide, phthalamide on the other.

It can be seen from the results given in the experimental portion that, excepting aromatic-*o*-nitrosamines and hydrazines and aminobenzenesulphonic acids which do not react at all, all the others give a fairly satisfactory yield of the substituted amides or hydrazides as the case may be. Aromatic acid amides do not react with aryl amines. In case of hydrazine hydrate and urea, whatever may be the quantity of the hydrate taken (one or two molecules), semicarbazide is always obtained to the complete exclusion of the equally expected carbonylhydrazide. The advantages offered by this method are that—

- (a) the reactions are well controlled,
- (b) the method gives good yield, and
- (c) the products obtained by this method are generally pure and seldom require further purification.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The amide (1 mol.) and the amine or hydrazine (2 mols.) mixed with sufficient amyl alcohol are heated over a free flame under reflux, till the evolution of ammonia which is very profuse in the beginning becomes negligible. The product is purified by means of very dilute hydrochloric acid which dissolves away the unchanged base, as also most of the unreacted amide. Special methods of purification, analytical results of new compounds, and only the yield and melting point of known compounds are given. Substances No. 1—20 were obtained from an amine and urea.

1. Carbanilide from anilin (m.p. 238°; yield, 80%).
2. Di-*m*-tolylurea from *m*-toluidine (m.p. 232°; yield 70%). Cosack (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 1449) gave m.p. 217° while Gatterman and Cantzler (*Ber.*, 1888, 25, 1069) gave m.p. 208°.
3. Di-*p*-tolylurea from *p*-toluidine (m.p. 262-63°; yield 80%).
4. *m*-Dinitrodiphenylurea from *m*-nitroaniline (yield, 70%). A pasty mass is obtained which is to be pressed on a Buchner funnel and dried in a desiccator.
5. *p*-Dinitrodiphenylurea from *p*-nitroaniline (m.p. 310°; yield, 80%).
6. Di- β -naphthylurea from β -naphthylamine (m.p. 309° decomp.; yield, 95%) (*cf.* Guha and Saletore, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 574).

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7. Di-*o*-naphthylurea from *o*-naphthylamin (m.p. 296° decomp.; yield, 95%). Guha and Saletore (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.
8. *pp*-Diacetylamino-diphenylurea from acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine (m.p. 344°; yield, 85%).
9. Dibenzylurea from benzylamine (m.p. 167°; yield, 95%).
10. *m*-Dihydroxydiphenylurea, from *m*-aminophenol, crystallises from alcohol (m.p. 215° decomp.; yield, 80%). (Found: N, 12.16. C₁₃H₁₂O₃N₂ requires N, 12.3 per cent.).
11. *p*-Dihydroxydiphenylurea, from *p*-aminophenol, crystallises from alcohol (m.p. 288° decomp.; yield, 95%). (Found: N, 12.21. C₁₃H₁₂O₃N₂ requires N, 12.3 per cent.).
12. 2:4-Dihydroxytetrahydro-1:2:3:4-quinazoline from *o*-aminobenzoic acid (m.p. 353° decomp.; yield, 80%) (*cf. J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1611; 1917, 39, 2437).
13. *o*-Phenyleneurea from *o*-phenylenediamine (m.p. 311°; yield, 95%).
14. *m*-Phenyleneurea (polymerised product) from *m*-phenylenediaminehydrochloride (m.p. 310° decomp.; yield, 93%).
15. Diphenyleneurea from benzidine (sublimation and darkening at 300°; yield, 90%).
16. Semicarbazide from hydrazine hydrate (m.p. 97°; yield, 76%). Care should be taken in avoiding a large quantity of amyl alcohol. Addition of ethyl alcohol to the reaction mixture is useful.
17. Diphenylcarbohydrazide from phenylhydrazine (m.p. 167° after previous softening at 158°; yield, 95%).
18. *pp*-Dinitrodiphenylcarbohydrazide, from *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine formed yellow crystals from benzene or glacial acetic acid (m.p. 361°; yield 50%). (Found: N, 25.2. C₁₃H₁₂O₅N₆ requires N, 25.3 per cent.).
19. *pp*-Dibromodiphenylcarbohydrazide, from *p*-bromophenylhydrazine. Yellowish crystals from glacial acetic acid turn violet after sometime (m.p. 236° decomp.; yield, 85%). (Found: N, 13.9. C₁₃H₁₂ON₄Br₂ requires N, 14.0 per cent.).
20. (a) 1-Phenyl-2-phenylamino-5-thiol-1:3:4-triazole soluble in alkali (m.p. 210°);
(b) 2:5-Endoxy-1:3:4-triazole soluble in water (m.p. 250°);

- (c) 2-Keto-5-phenylamino-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole insoluble in water or alkali (m.p. 246°).

These three compounds were obtained from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (total yield, 60%), and were separated by the method of Guha and Sen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 43).

21. *p*-Monoacetylaminodiphenylurea from acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and phenylurea (m.p. 244° decomp.; yield, 95%).

22. *pp*-Diacetylaminodiphenylthiourea from acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and thiourea (m.p. 244° decomp.; yield, 50%).

23. Thiocarbanilide from aniline and thiourea (m.p. 152°; yield, 95%).

24. 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide, instead of *pp*-diphenylthiocarbonylhydrazide as expected, from phenylhydrazine and thiourea (m.p. 198° decomp.; yield, 70%).

25. Oxanilide from aniline and oxamide (m.p. 252°; yield, 90%).

26. Oxalyldiphenylhydrazide from phenylhydrazine and oxamide (m.p. 274°; yield, 30%).

27. *pp*-Diacetylaminodiphenyloxamide from acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and oxamide (m.p. above 370°; yield, 60%). The method of purification is different from the general method. The compound being easily hydrolysable by hydrochloric acid, the reactants are dissolved away by means of warm dilute alcohol leaving behind the product. The dihydrochloride was prepared by evaporating the hydrolysed compound to dryness. The hydrochloride and the free base are colourless, crystalline compounds. (Found: N, 16.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_4Cl_2$ (dihydrochloride) requires N, 16.4 per cent).

28. Malonanilide from aniline and malonamide (m.p. 222°; yield, 95%).

29. Malonyldiphenylhydrazide from phenylhydrazine and malonamide (m.p. 194-95°; yield, 90%). Asher (*Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 1024) gave m.p. 184°. Freund and Goldschmidt (*Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 1241) gave m.p. 187°.

30. *pp*-Diacetylaminodiphenylmalonamide from acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and malonamide (m.p. 235° decomp.; yield, 60%). The same method of purification as for the corresponding oxamide compound (No. 27) was followed. It crystallises from 88 per cent

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alcohol. (Found: N, 15.9. $C_{15}H_{18}O_2N_4Cl_2$ (dihydrochloride) requires N, 15.8 per cent.).

31. Succinamide from aniline and succinamide (m.p. 228°; yield, 50%).

32. Succinyldiphenylhydrazide from phenylhydrazine and succinamide (m.p. 207-8°; yield, 80%). Fischer and Passmore (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2734) gave m.p. 201° decomp.

33. *pp*-Diacetylamino*diphenylsuccinamide* from acetyl-*p*-phenylenediamine and succinamide (m.p. 347° decomp., yield, 60%). The method of purification is similar to compounds No. 27 and No. 30. The colourless, crystalline base (m.p. 172°) obtained by hydrolysis was analysed. (Found: N, 19.8. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2N_4$ requires N, 20 per cent.).

34. Acetanilide from aniline and acetamide on complete removal of amyl alcohol and crystallisation of the residue from hot water (m.p. 114°; yield, 80%).

p-Aminobenzoic acid reacts with urea to give a 90 per cent. yield of a white amorphous compound (m.p. above 370°) which could not be purified further and gave varying results on analysis. The compound thus remains unidentified.

No definite compound could be isolated from the tarry mass formed in the reaction between acetamide and phenylhydrazine.

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